

iPhone application to support commuters

J.v. Beusekom, P.G. Poulsen, and L.L. Pedersen

DTU Software technology, Technical University of Denmark
s093251@student.dtu.dk, s093263@student.dtu.dk, s093278@student.dtu.dk

The burning of fossil fuels has always had a great influence on the environment, but the true consequences of the problem have not been recognized until a few decades ago. In recent years a lot of the greatest nations have worked together in search of solutions to the problems caused by CO₂ emissions. A lot of attention has been given to the burning of oil and how it would be possible to reduce the use of fossil fuels. In Denmark, the transport sector is responsible for about 30% of all CO₂ emissions, which is something the government, among others, is trying to reduce. One way of reducing the CO₂ emissions made by cars, is by getting new types of cars on the market that do not use gasoline as their primary source of fuel, namely electric cars and hybrid-cars. Although this would help to reduce CO₂ emissions, another part of the problem lies with peoples' driving mentality. Often you see people taking the car over long distances alone, which is both uneconomic and unnecessarily damaging to the environment. It is obvious that it would be preferable if you could make people drive together. The greatest challenge about making people do this is to create a network for people to use when finding driving partners, without it becoming a burden or taking a lot of time. In recent years a new kind of technology has emerged, smartphones, which allow users to browse the Internet, visit Facebook, Twitter and other social networks, using GPS along with a large amount of other functions. Among the so-called smartphones, Apple's iPhone is one of the most common. Our solution to the earlier mentioned problem with making people drive together is making an iPhone application that helps commuters find driving partners based upon their routes. The application is going to be implemented with Facebook and Twitter so that upon creating or requesting a ride it is possible to announce it, so that it is possible to find driving partners outside of the application as well. Our vision with the application is to create a large network of users and make carpooling more common than it is now, which ultimately would protect the environment. We have focused on making the application very user-friendly and easy-to-use, because it is important that people do not feel it is a burden to use it.

